

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 3-D CARBON/BISMALEIMIDE HEAT-RESISTANT COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Mechanical properties of three-dimensional (3-D) carbon/bismaleimide woven composite were investigated and compared to two dimensional textile laminates of the same material system under static tension, compression, and compression-after-impact tests. Bismaleimide (BMI) 5250-4 resin from Cytek, Inc. was chosen as the matrix in this study due to it being a candidate resin for use in high-temperature composite airframe structures for next generation supersonic transport. A near net-shape dry 3-D preform comprising pi-by-four orientation carbon fibers reinforced with orthogonal z-direction fibers was prepared after which molding took place utilizing the resin film infusion (RFI) process. A high volume fraction of about 56% was attained by this 3-D processing due to the use of straight in-plane fibers. Experimental results showed the longitudinal modulus of both materials to be fairly similar, though the transverse modulus of the 3-D composite was slightly higher. Both the longitudinal tensile and compressive strength of the 3-D composite were approximately 6% lower than those of the 2-D laminate, while the compression-after-impact strength of the 3-D was significantly higher than that of the 2-D composite. The impact damage were also examined by the ultrasonic scanning method.

KEYWORDS: 3-D composite, carbon/bismaleimide composite, heat resistant materials, textile, resin film infusion, compression test, tension test, CAI strength

INTRODUCTION

The application fields of polymeric composite structures have been increasingly expanded in the past few decades especially for the structures where weight are at a premium. A typical example of this kind of structures is composite airframes. After twenty years of scheduled flights of Concorde, the next generation supersonic transports are expected to be developed and manufactured in the near future for replying to the estimated air travel growth [1]. In order to produce an economically viable supersonic transport, it is required to develop and apply high performance polymeric composite materials which will be durable for long term high temperature adverse environments and more tolerable against impact damages [2,3]. Laminated plates of fiber reinforced plastics have been widely adopted to the composite structures as load bearing components. However, increased use of advanced composite materials has required that processes other than traditional prepreg layups and autoclave cure be developed to meet design properties and damage tolerance requirements of structures [4-6].

Three-dimensional (3-D) textile composites offer potential improvements in the ability of a composite structure to survive a high energy impact with minimal decrease of strength [7-9].

In this work, fundamental mechanical properties of 3-D carbon/bismaleimide composite plates were investigated experimentally including in-plane tensile/compressive elastic constants, static tensile and compressive strength, and compression strength after impact. A near net-shape dry fiber preform was formed by pi-by-four fiber orientation in a x-y plain with orthogonal z-direction fiber reinforcement. Firstly, our research work was concentrated on attaining a higher volume fraction of a 3-D dry fiber preform. Secondly, resin film infusion (RFI) processes were studied for making thin plates of carbon/bismaleimide 3-D composites. All specimens were cut out from the plates. In this study, Cytec 5250-4 resin was used for RFI processes, and our estimated volume fraction was about 54 to 57%. In-plane tension and compression tests were carried out and stiffness and strength were measured and compared to two-dimensional (2-D) quasi-isotropic materials which have been laminated of dry cloth plies, and about the same volume fraction values. Our experimental results show that the longitudinal modulus of both materials is quite similar, but that the transverse modulus of the 3-D is slightly higher. In terms of strength, the longitudinal tensile and also compressive strength of the 3-D composite was approximately 6% lower than those of the 2-D laminate. The CAI test was carried out based on the SACMA method. The thickness of our specimens were all about 5 mm. The 3-D composites showed a much higher compressive strength after impact damage than that of 2-D ones. The 3-D composites maintained about 68% values after the impact damage energy of 1500 in-lb/in, and 60% for 2000 in-lb/in. The damage area was examined by the ultrasonic scanning method, and we found both composites have about the same projected damaged areas for these impact energy levels. However, smaller and more distributed cracks seemed to be formed during the impact for the 3-D composites, and this characteristics contributed the compressive strength of the 3-D materials to keep higher levels.

WEAVING PROCESSES FOR THREE-DIMENSIONAL (3-D) FABRICS

The dry fabric preforms were produced by our thrusting apparatus which is schematically shown in Fig.2.1. All 3-D fabrics were formed in two steps. The first step is arranging of in-plane fibers to make a lamina. In this work, these were arranged along 0^0 , 45^0 or 90^0 line by engaging with many restriction members such as pins, located with a predetermined pitch on a frame[9]. The second step is insertion of z-direction fibers. The thrusting apparatus for z-direction fiber is consisted mainly of (1) a movable support table which supports the frame and is movable by a predetermined pitch, (2) a press plate which presses the laminated fiber layers, and guides the needles, (3) the perforating needles which make pre-holes in the fiber layers to prevent from damage caused by the insertion of the z-direction fibers, (4) the inserting needles which thrust z-direction fibers, and (5) a lock yarn needle which inserts a lock yarn into loop of z-direction fibers. These z-fibers are thrust by many inserting needles, which are arranged in a series, into the laminated fiber layers.

Details of the weaving processes are:

- (1) pushing the laminated fiber layers by press plate,
- (2) making pre-holes to the laminated fiber layers by perforating needles,
- (3) thrusting the inserting needles to the laminated fiber layers with z-direction fibers,
- (4) making loops of z-direction fibers by a little going back of inserting needles, and inserting a lock yarn into the loops,

- (5) pulling back the inserting needles and tightening the z-direction fibers.

A sample of our dry fabric preforms and a schematic drawing are shown in Fig.2.2 and Fig.2.3. The advantages of this production method are;

- (1) high quality and high volume fraction of 3-D fabric, because the lamination is supported by pins until the insertion of z-direction fibers are completed, and fiber straightness is maintained, and because we use perforated needles, press plate and special tension device ,
- (2) capability of high productivity, because z-direction fibers are inserted in a series together ,
- (3) capability for production of complex shape fabric by developing of frame and table.

FABRICATION PROCESSES OF BMI-RESIN COMPOSITES

To fabricate a composite part, it is necessary, as in the case of 3-dimensional fabrics, to have molding process performed including impregnation and curing of resin for the preforms which are made of only the "dry" base reinforcement fiber materials. In this study, we have used the resin film infusion (RFI) process as molding method. The principle of this concept is shown in Fig.3.1. The resin has been prepared in the form of a film or a panel beforehand. The resin film/panel was applied to both sides of the preform. Then, they were heated in a vacuum environment to have resin melted and impregnated into the preform by capillary action. Further heating of the assembly was accomplished to cure the impregnated resin. This method used much simpler equipment and operations compared to the general resin transfer molding where resin was impregnated into the preform by applying pressure. Therefore, this method can be considered advantageous for applications to aircraft skins, etc. where relative simpler shapes of preforms are used, because the satisfactory quality level of formed parts can be assured as well as a shorter molding time [10]. Figure 3.2 shows the equipment used for RFI process. The center of the equipment is a vacuum chamber. It can be used to fabricate a part of maximum 200mmW x 300mmL using the metal mold die placed in the vacuum chamber. Figure 3-3 shows the molding cycle. The resin was melted and impregnated at temperature of 100⁰C in a vacuum environment of 540mmHg minimum. The specimens were cured at 191⁰C. After that, they were applied to post-cure process at temperature of 227⁰C. Figure 3-4 shows the section of specimen. The satisfactory quality parts which have almost free from voids, interlaminar cracks, etc. can be fabricated up to maximum thickness of 6mm by the above process.

Table 3-1 shows the specification of the specimens used in this work. The 5 axes 3 dimensional (with 4 in-plane axes directions in 0°, -45°, +45°, 90° and additional one axis in thickness direction) composite (3-D) and 2 dimensional composite (2-D) was prepared. 2-D specimen aims at giving the reference. 3-D's preform is the mentioned 3D-fabric and 2-D's preform is lamination of dry cloths that is pre-impregnated textile. Both 3-D and 2-D specimens were fabricated by the same molding process. Two types of carbon fiber, MR50K of Mitsubishi Rayon and T900 of Toray, were used. MR50K was used for in-plane direction fiber as a plenty of data were available for this material. It was used as a yarn for 3-D specimen, and satin woven fabric for 2-D specimen. T900 twist yarn was used for 3-D through-the-thickness direction fiber. The used resin was bismaleimide resin #5250-4-RTM of Cytec. This resin was chosen from several different types of bismaleimide resins by

comparing the previous test results of their characteristics on better workability, and less possibilities of having voids and/or interlaminar cracks.

TESTING

Specimen Configurations and Testing Methods

Various test methods have been investigated to evaluate the stiffness and strength of textile composites properly, as these materials tend to be less homogeneous than conventional tape laminates, and are known their failure processes are significantly different [11,12]. There seems to be little data base, especially for the 3-D composites, to build up a standard test method. In this study, we focused on the mechanical properties of those compared to the 2-D laminates which we have already had some experiences and test results. Specimen configurations of in-plane tension, compression, and CAI test are shown Fig. 4.1. The SACMA(Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association) method was adopted for the CAI test method [13]. Specimens were impacted at room temperature with a spherical tip impactor at 1500 or 2000 inch-pounds/inch thickness of the energy level. Tensile tests were conducted on the MTS machine under load controlled mode. The compressive tests and CAI test were conducted on the Instron machine under displacement controlled mode at a crosshead speed of 0.4 mm/min and 0.5 mm/min respectively.

Tensile Properties

The 5mm long strain gages were bonded at both surfaces in the longitudinal and transverse directions. Four strain data with loading one were recorded to a developed digital data acquisition system using personal computer. Fig.4.2 and Fig 4.3 are the sample stress-strain curves of 2-D and 3-D specimens. As seen in these figures, the longitudinal modulus of both materials is quite similar, but that the transverse modulus of the 3-D is slightly higher. In terms of strength, the longitudinal tensile strength of the 3-D's are about 6% lower than that of the 2-D laminates.

Compressive Properties

Similar to tensile test specimens, 3mm long strain gages were bonded at both surfaces and measured and recorded by the data acquisition system. The stress-strain curves of 2-D and 3-D specimen under static compressive loads are shown at Fig.4.4 and Fig.4.5, respectively. Again, the longitudinal modulus of both materials is quite similar, but that the transverse modulus of the 3-D is slightly higher. The compressive strength of the 3-D's are about 6% lower than that of the 2-D laminates.

Compression-after-impact Properties

Out-of-plane impact damages were investigated by a ultrasonic imaging system prior to compressive failure tests of CAI specimens. The damage area was measured and examined by the ultrasonic C-scanning method, and our data showed both of 2-D and 3-D composites have about the same projected damaged areas for 1500 and 2000in-lb-in impact energy levels. However, as seen in Fig. 4.6 and Fig. 4.7, smaller and more distributed cracks seemed to be formed during the impact for the 3-D composites. The growth of interlaminar failures was observed to be arrested by the through-thickness reinforcement fibers. Load vs. strain curves

of compression tests after 1500 or 2000 in-lb-in impact damages were shown in Fig.4.8 to Fig. 4.11. Strains were measured at the locations of the both sides, S1,S2,S3,S4, as indicated in the SACMA recommendations. Our experiments showed that the 3-D composites maintained about 68% values after the impact damage energy of 1500 in-lb/in, and 60% for 2000 in-lb/in.

Properties of 3-D Composites

The longitudinal modulus of both materials is quite similar, but that the transverse modulus of the 3-D is slightly higher. Both the tensile and compressive strength of the 3-D composite were approximately 6% lower than those of the 2-D laminate, while the 3-D composites showed a much higher compressive strength after impact damage than that of the 2-D composite. The 3-D composites maintained about 68% values after the impact damage energy of 1500 in-lb/in, and 60% for 2000 in-lb/in. Preliminary ultrasonic C-scan data indicated the z-fiber in the 3-D composite contributed to arrest the propagations of distributed cracks generated by out-of-plane impacts. Experimental results are summarized in Table 5.1

CONCLUSIONS

A high volume fraction of about 56% was attained in this work for the 3D carbon/bismaleimide composite which was molded by resin film infusion process. Although the data are limited, the compression-after-impact strength of the 3-D composites were significantly higher than that of the 2-D composites.

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Fig. 2-1 Weaving Apparatus

Fig. 2-2 Three-Dimensional Dry Fabric Preform

Fig. 2-3 Photograph of Three-Dimensional Dry Fabric Preform

Fig. 3-1 Resin Film Infusion (RFI) Process

Fig. 3-2 Resin Film Infusion (RFI) Process Equipment

Table 3-1 Specification of Specimens

Sample	3D	2D
Reinforcement	5-axis 3-D Fabric	Laminated 2D-Textile
Fiber		
In the Plain Direction	MR50K	MR50K
In the Thickness Direction	T900	—
Matrix	#5250-4-RTM	#5250-4-RTM
Fiber Arrangement		
in the Plain Direction	Quasi-isotropic	Quasi-isotropic
in the Thickness	Pitch: 3 ^L × 3 ^W (mm)	—

Fig. 3-4 Section of the 3-D Composite Specimen

Fig. 4-1 Specimen Configurations

Fig. 4-2 Stress-Strain curves in Tension Test (2-D Specimen)

Fig. 4-3 Stress-Strain curves in Tension Test (3-D Specimen)

Fig. 4-4 Stress-Strain curves in Compression Test (2-D Specimen)

Fig. 4-5 Stress-Strain curves in Compression Test (3-D Specimen)

Fig. 4-7 Impact Damage Area (2-D CAI Specimen, 1500in-lb-in)

Fig. 4-8 Impact Damage Area (3-D CAI Specimen, 1500in-lb-in)

Fig. 4-9 Stress-Strain Curves in CAI Test (2-D Specimen, 1500in-lb-in)

Fig. 4-10 Stress-Strain Curves in CAI Test (2-D Specimen, 2000in-lb-in)

Fig. 4-11 Stress-Strain Curves in CAI Test (3-D Specimen, 1500in-lb-in)

Fig. 4-12 Stress-Strain Curves in CAI Test (3-D Specimen, 2000in-lb-in)

Table 5-1 Test Results of the 3-D and 2-D Composites

Specimen Type		Thickness [mm]	Vf [%]	Modulus [GPa] mean : s.d.		Poisson's Ratio mean : s.d.		Strength [MPa] mean : s.d.	
Tension Test	2-D	2.30	64.0	61.26	0.50	0.340	0.01	876.0	24.0
	3-D	2.10	54.5	57.63	3.10	0.246	0.01	823.1	23.0
Compression Test	2-D	2.30	63.6	50.55	3.20	0.266	0.06	665.1	38.0
	3-D	2.10	54.5	50.67	5.00	0.196	0.02	574.9	32.0
CAI Test (1500in-lb-in)	2-D	5.04	56.9	51.21	—	—	—	266.8	—
	3-D	5.04	56.5	54.54	1.60	—	—	393.4	26.0
CAI Test (2000in-lb-in)	2-D	5.04	56.9	50.71	—	—	—	260.0	—
	3-D	5.04	56.5	54.20	1.60	—	—	344.3	26.0